

Fig. S2. Full-length images of Western blots carried out in hypothalamus. Considering the number of samples per treatment, we carried out 3 gels/membranes per protein in which we have distributed the samples in such a way that there is a representative number of each treatment in each gel/membrane (in some cases external samples to this publication were included in the membranes in order to take advantage of the procedure and the reagents). Once observed the results of the protein in its phosphorylated form, we perform a stripping of the membrane in order to use it by incubating the total form of the same protein. Once the photograph that most represent the trend of the graphics has been chosen, a cut of the membrane (represented here by a black square) was carried out to show in Figs. 5 and 7.

Bsx hindbrain

Tubulin hindbrain

p-Creb hindbrain

Creb hindbrain

p-FoxO1 hindbrain

FoxO1 hindbrain

